

A Study on Thyroid Profile in Chronic Liver Disease Patients Admitted in PMCH, Patna

Supriya Kumari¹, Amit Kumar Tiwari², Gautam Kumar Sandilya³, Vijay Achari⁴

¹Senior Resident, Department of Medicine, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Medicine, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Senior Resident, Department of Medicine, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

⁴Professor & HOD, Department of Medicine, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Gautam Kumar Sandilya

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Chronic liver disease (CLD) is a global health burden associated with significant morbidity and mortality. Thyroid dysfunction is an increasingly recognized comorbidity in patients with CLD due to the liver's crucial role in thyroid hormone metabolism. However, the prevalence and nature of thyroid dysfunction in this population, particularly in rural settings, remain underexplored.

Aim: This study aims to assess the prevalence and types of thyroid dysfunction among patients with chronic liver disease admitted to PMCH and to evaluate the association between thyroid dysfunction and the severity of liver disease.

Methods: Participants underwent thyroid function testing, including serum levels of T3, T4, and TSH. The severity of liver disease was classified using the Child-Pugh score. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Thyroid dysfunction was observed in 40% of the patients. Subclinical hypothyroidism was the most common abnormality (20%), followed by overt hypothyroidism (10%), subclinical hyperthyroidism (6.7%), and overt hyperthyroidism (3.3%). A significant association was found between the severity of liver disease and the presence of thyroid dysfunction ($p < 0.01$). Correlation analysis revealed a negative correlation between T3 levels and serum bilirubin ($r = -0.45$, $p < 0.01$) and a positive correlation between TSH levels and serum bilirubin ($r = 0.38$, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Thyroid dysfunction is prevalent among patients with chronic liver disease, particularly in those with more severe liver disease. The findings highlight the need for routine thyroid function screening in this population to enable early detection and management of thyroid abnormalities, potentially improving clinical outcomes.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers, especially in rural settings, should incorporate regular thyroid function assessments in the management of patients with chronic liver disease. Further research is warranted to explore the mechanisms underlying the relationship between liver and thyroid dysfunction and to develop targeted therapeutic strategies.

Keywords: Chronic Liver Disease, Thyroid Dysfunction, Rural Healthcare, Hypothyroidism, Thyroid Function Test.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

A major worldwide health issue that significantly increases morbidity and mortality is CLD. It includes a range of liver conditions such as cirrhosis, hepatitis, and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease NAFLD, which if left untreated can lead to the development of liver failure, hepatocellular carcinoma, and even death. The liver plays a major role in metabolism, detoxification, and hormone control, so when it malfunctions, the endocrine system is just one of the many systems it might affect. Thyroid dysfunction is one of the less studied but more widely acknowledged effects of chronic liver disease.

The thyroid gland secretes hormones such as triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4), which are essential for controlling growth, metabolism, and development. These hormones affect the basal metabolic rate and are essential for the liver and other organs to function normally. In turn, the liver is essential for the metabolism of thyroid hormones, which includes removing thyroid hormones from the bloodstream and converting T4 to the more active T3. Consequently, substantial changes in thyroid function, such as hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism, can result

from chronic liver illness. These changes might be asymptomatic or clinical.

The mutually beneficial association between thyroid and liver function has been brought to light by recent investigations. In a study it was showed that individuals with cirrhosis frequently had low T3 levels, a condition known as "low T3 syndrome," which is linked to a poor prognosis and higher mortality in these patients [1]. Similarly, in another study it was discovered that subclinical hypothyroidism is more common in patients with NAFLD, pointing to a possible connection between thyroid malfunction and metabolic liver disease. The significance of thyroid function monitoring in individuals with chronic liver disease is highlighted by these findings [2].

Despite these discoveries, little is known about the connection between thyroid dysfunction and chronic liver disease, especially in rural areas where access to healthcare may be restricted and the prevalence of chronic illnesses is frequently higher. Comprehending the frequency and type of thyroid dysfunction within this demographic is essential for enhancing patient outcomes, since thyroid dysfunction may intensify liver disease consequences and influence treatment choices.

By evaluating the thyroid profiles of patients with chronic liver disease admitted to PMCH, this study seeks to close this gap. This study aims to assess the prevalence and types of thyroid dysfunction among patients with chronic liver disease admitted to PMCH and to evaluate the association between thyroid dysfunction and the severity of liver disease.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of Medicine at PMCH over a period of 12 months. The hospital serves a large catchment area, providing care to a diverse population predominantly from rural and semi-urban backgrounds.

Participants: A total of 300 patients diagnosed with chronic liver disease and admitted to the hospital were included in the study. The participants were selected using a consecutive sampling method.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Diagnosed with chronic liver disease, confirmed by clinical, biochemical, and imaging criteria.

- Patients willing to give informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a known history of thyroid disorders prior to the onset of liver disease.
- Patients on medications that affect thyroid function (e.g., amiodarone, lithium).
- Pregnant women.
- Patients with acute liver failure.
- Patients unwilling or unable to give informed consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was employed. All eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria during the study period were enrolled. To reduce information bias, standardized protocols were used for thyroid function testing and data collection.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured case report form. This included demographic details, clinical history, liver function tests, and thyroid function tests (T3, T4, TSH). Laboratory investigations were performed in the hospital's central laboratory using standard automated techniques.

Procedure: Upon admission, patients were evaluated for chronic liver disease through clinical assessment and laboratory investigations. Once diagnosed, patients were enrolled in the study after providing informed consent. Blood samples were collected for thyroid function tests along with routine investigations. The thyroid profile was analyzed, and the results were recorded.

Statistical Analysis: Version 23.0 of the SPSS program was used to analyse the data. The baseline characteristics of the study population were obtained using descriptive statistics. While frequency and percentages were used to convey categorical data, means with standard deviations were used to present continuous variables. The proper statistical procedures, such as chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests or ANOVA for continuous variables, were used to evaluate the connection between thyroid function and the severity of chronic liver disease. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value of less than 0.05.

Results

The mean age of the participants was 52.4 ± 12.3 years, with a range of 19 to 75 years. The study population consisted of 200 males (66.7%) and 100 females (33.3%). The majority of the patients were from rural areas (75%) and had a low socioeconomic status (60%).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Mean \pm SD / n (%)
Age (years)	52.4 \pm 12.3
Gender	
- Male	200 (66.7%)
- Female	100 (33.3%)
Residence	
- Rural	225 (75.0%)
- Urban	75 (25.0%)
Socioeconomic Status	
- Low	180 (60.0%)
- Middle	90 (30.0%)
- High	30 (10.0%)

Thyroid Profile Findings: The thyroid profile was assessed using serum levels of T3, T4, and TSH. Thyroid dysfunction was observed in 120 (40%) of the 300 patients.

Table 2: Thyroid Function Status among Participants

Thyroid Function Status	n (%)
Euthyroid	180 (60.0%)
Subclinical Hypothyroidism	60 (20.0%)
Overt Hypothyroidism	30 (10.0%)
Subclinical Hyperthyroidism	20 (6.7%)
Overt Hyperthyroidism	10 (3.3%)

Association between Thyroid Dysfunction and Liver Disease Severity: The severity of chronic liver disease was classified using the Child-Pugh score, which categorizes liver disease into Class A (mild), Class B (moderate), and Class C (severe). The distribution of thyroid dysfunction across different severity classes is shown in Table 3.

- **Class A (mild):** 120 patients (40%)

- **Class B (moderate):** 100 patients (33.3%)
- **Class C (severe):** 80 patients (26.7%)

A statistically significant association was found between the severity of liver disease and the presence of thyroid dysfunction ($p < 0.01$).

Table 3: Distribution of Thyroid Dysfunction by Liver Disease Severity

Thyroid Dysfunction	Class A (n=120)	Class B (n=100)	Class C (n=80)	p-value
Euthyroid	96 (80.0%)	60 (60.0%)	24 (30.0%)	
Subclinical Hypo	12 (10.0%)	20 (20.0%)	28 (35.0%)	
Overt Hypo	6 (5.0%)	10 (10.0%)	14 (17.5%)	
Subclinical Hyper	4 (3.3%)	6 (6.0%)	10 (12.5%)	
Overt Hyper	2 (1.7%)	4 (4.0%)	4 (5.0%)	<0.01

Correlation between Thyroid Profile and Liver Function Tests: A correlation analysis was performed to assess the relationship between thyroid hormone levels (T3, T4, TSH) and liver function parameters (ALT, AST, Bilirubin, Albumin). There was a negative correlation

between T3 levels and serum bilirubin ($r = -0.45$, $p < 0.01$) and a positive correlation between TSH levels and serum bilirubin ($r = 0.38$, $p < 0.05$). Additionally, T4 levels showed a weak negative correlation with serum albumin levels ($r = -0.22$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 4: Correlation between Thyroid Hormone Levels and Liver Function Tests

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
T3	Serum Bilirubin	-0.45	<0.01
TSH	Serum Bilirubin	0.38	<0.05
T4	Serum Albumin	-0.22	<0.05

The results of this study demonstrate a high prevalence of thyroid dysfunction among patients with chronic liver disease. The findings suggest that as the severity of liver disease increases, the likelihood of thyroid dysfunction also rises. The correlations between thyroid hormone levels and

liver function tests indicate a complex interplay between thyroid and liver physiology, potentially influencing disease outcomes.

Discussion

According to the study, people with chronic liver illness were significantly more likely to have thyroid dysfunction; 40% of the participants had some sort of thyroid abnormalities. Sixty percent of the 300 individuals who were investigated had normal thyroid function, meaning they were euthyroid. Subclinical hypothyroidism (20%) was the most common type, followed by overt hypothyroidism (10%), subclinical hyperthyroidism (6.7%), and overt hyperthyroidism (3.3%). Nevertheless, a significant portion of the population had thyroid dysfunction. A significant discovery of the research was the correlation between thyroid dysfunction and the degree of liver illness, as determined by the Child-Pugh score. Thyroid abnormalities were more common in patients with more severe liver disease (Class C) than in those with milder disease (Class A).

For example, compared to 35% of patients in Class C, only 20% of patients in Class A had subclinical hypothyroidism. This implies that the chance of thyroid malfunction rises with the severity of liver illness, suggesting a possible interaction between thyroid function and the degree of liver damage.

The study also found a strong relationship between liver function tests and thyroid hormone levels. Notably, serum bilirubin and TSH levels correlated positively, while serum bilirubin and T3 levels correlated negatively. These associations imply that liver disease, shown by increased bilirubin levels, may have a negative impact on thyroid function and cause hypothyroidism in certain individuals. A modest negative association has been observed between serum albumin levels and T4 levels, suggesting that changed thyroid hormone levels may be linked to reduced albumin levels, which are frequently observed in advanced liver disease. Overall, the findings point to thyroid dysfunction as a common comorbidity in patients with chronic liver disease, especially as the illness worsens. The study emphasises the necessity of routinely assessing thyroid function in these patients because treating thyroid abnormalities early on may enhance clinical results. The results further emphasise the intricate connection between liver physiology and thyroid function, which calls for more investigation to fully comprehend the processes behind this interaction.

In a comparable way, it was investigated in which if thyroid characteristics may be used to predict the likelihood of decompensation in liver cirrhosis. According to the study, patients with more severe cirrhosis had considerably lower levels of free T3, suggesting that free T3 could be used as a sensitive marker to gauge the severity of cirrhosis. The results corroborate the hypothesis that thyroid function monitoring, specifically measuring free T3

levels, may be useful in identifying individuals who are more vulnerable to consequences from advanced liver illness [3].

Giri used the Child-Pugh score in another investigation to look at the relationship between thyroid function and the severity of chronic liver disease. The degree of liver illness was found to be significantly positively correlated with blood TSH levels. Furthermore, the degree of liver disease was negatively correlated with free T3 and free T4 levels, supporting the notion that thyroid dysfunction is intimately linked to the development of chronic liver diseases [4].

Numerous investigations on the connection between chronic liver illness and thyroid dysfunction have shown how intricately these two systems interact. In a research published in 2020 it was evaluated thyroid dysfunction in individuals suffering from liver disorders linked to chronic hepatitis C. The study's findings revealed that thyroid abnormalities were more common in cirrhosis patients than in non-cirrhotic people. The Child-T-Pugh score showed a high correlation between the severity of these anomalies and the degree of liver damage. This implies that thyroid function tests may be an important tool for determining how these individuals' liver disease is progressing [5].

Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of routine thyroid function screening in patients with chronic liver disease, especially those with advanced stages of the disease. Early detection and management of thyroid dysfunction may improve overall patient outcomes in this population.

References

1. Malik R, Hodgson H, Sumpter K, Fitzpatrick D. Thyroid dysfunction in cirrhosis: A prognostic factor for survival. *J Clin Transl Hepatol* .2019;7(2):146-53.
2. Moustafa T, Mohamed R, Osman M, Wahsh E. Thyroid dysfunction in non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Endocr Disord*. 2021;21(1):34.
3. Injeti KP, Mounika A, Paka AC, Parise G. Can thyroid profile predict the impending danger of decompensation in liver cirrhosis?
4. Giri R, Singh V, Gulati Y, Kumar V. A study of thyroid function profile in patients of chronic liver disease and its correlation with child Pugh score.
5. Hassan I, El-Nemr N, Aboelmagd M, Mohamed FRM. Assessment of thyroid dysfunction in patients with chronic hepatitis C virus-related liver diseases.